

Directive Speaking Actions in Indonesian Speaking in Children with Speech Delays

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Abstract:- This study describes the mastery of speech acts in Indonesian speech in children with speech delays. The focus of this research is the mastery of directive speech acts in Indonesian speech in children with speech delays. Children with speech delays are children whose level of quality of speech development is imperfect in pronouncing words and then has a limited vocabulary and has difficulty naming objects. The purpose of this study is to describe the mastery of directive speech acts. In this study, a qualitative descriptive research method was used. The data source of this study was one child with a speech delay aged 9;0. The data of this research are words, phrases, and sentences that contain directive speech acts. The data collection used in this research includes observation, fishing, recording, and field notes. The stages of data collection are making observations, recording speeches, transcribing speeches, and validating data. In analyzing the data, the pragmatic equivalent method was used. Data analysis procedures include reducing data, interpreting data, and concluding. Based on data analysis, it can be concluded that children with speech delays can use directive speech acts. The directive speech acts controlled by V are asking, ordering, forbidding, inviting, and asking.

Keywords:- Speech; Directive Speech Act; Speech Delay Child.

I. INTRODUCTION

Every child has different language development. Children who experience speech delays usually experience language barriers. Leung & Kao (1999) said that a child is said to have a speech delay if his speech development is significantly below normal than children his age. This means that children who are the same age but have different speaking abilities can be said to have speech delays.

Khoiriyah, et al. (2016:37) states that speech delays in children can also cause children to have difficulty adapting and socializing with their surrounding environment. Environmental conditions that cause speech delays, namely social-economic conditions, an unfavorable environment, unpleasant behavior of parents or other people, inappropriate teaching techniques, too much hope for children, using two languages (bilingual), twins, functional delay, and children rarely get a stimulus from the environment. Children with speech delays have difficulty in assembling words so that it is

difficult to achieve various communicative goals. This can be seen from the resulting speech. Usually, children with speech delays have speech deficits. The speech deficit can be seen from the imperfections of speech in the use of language based on the intent and purpose being uttered so that it is difficult for the speech partner to understand.

Based on observations, when the research subject (S) was 3; 5, he was only able to speak *mama*, *papa*, *mba*, *emo*, *ya*, *aum*, *maem*. This shows that S has a speech delay. In this study, S was used as a child with speech delays and classified as mild mental retardation. Lumbantobing (2006:34) states that children with mild mental retardation are included in the educable group. This is the reason why children with speech delays are chosen who are classified as mild mental retardation and limited vocabulary.

An article discussing children with speech delays was once written by Syamsuardi (2015). The purpose of writing this article is to describe the factors that cause speech delays. The research subject in this article is one child with a speech delay aged 6;0. The research method in this article is qualitative in the form of a case study. The research findings in the article are (1) Aq's speaking ability shows that Aq's speech development is very low, (2) the factors that affect speech delay due to the emergence of two problems, namely (a) physical factors and (b) environmental factors, namely (i) family environment caused by a lack of understanding of parenting, parents' speaking style follows the style of speech children, (ii) the community environment.

Research on pragmatic competence has been conducted by Asih (2017). He studied children aged 2;0 to obtain data on acquisition and inhibiting factors in obtaining pragmatic competence. The research data were obtained from 25 videos taken via Youtube with the name @ItsJudysLife. The videos were then transcribed for data analysis. In the results of the research written by Asih, it was found that eight pragmatic competencies were mastered by children at the age of 2;0 to 4;0. The findings are shared knowledge (common ground), speech act (speech act), the target of speech (taking account to the addressee), joint attention (joint attention), convention and contrast (convention and contrast), taking turns, speaker's intention, and politeness expression. The inhibiting factor is the stimulus factor from the parents significantly and the age factor is not significant.

The speech of children with speech delays is interesting to study because the language development of children acquires their first language perfectly around the age of 5;0 (Steinberg, Nagata, and Aline, 2001:3-27; Harley, 2008:104). However, the language understood and produced by S aged 9;0 still limited. This can be proven by S when he was 9;0 he was only able to say a few words. S has not been able to compose sentences well. Therefore, this article focuses on the use of directive speech acts in Indonesian speech in children with speech delays.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Children with speech delays are children who have characteristics that are different from other children who are considered normal by society in general, especially in speaking. Children aged 2;0 who tend to be less precise in pronouncing words than at age 3;0 choose words that tend to be bad or when children aged 5;0 find it difficult to name an object, it is indicated that they are late in speaking. The child will tend to be unable to read (Papalia, et al., 2004: 252-253). This opinion is in line with the research subject in this article. Age 9;0 still has difficulty naming an object and has not been able to read. In general, children with speech delays have IQ below normal children. Children with IQ below the average are called mentally retarded or mentally retarded. Shetty (2012: 104-105) says the causes that affect speech delay are mental retardation, hearing loss, maturation delay, expressive language disorder, bilingualism, psychosocial deprivation, autism, selective mutism, receptive aphasia, and cerebral palsy. This opinion is relevant to this study, namely the research subject experienced speech delays due to mental retardation.

Leung and Cao (1999) stated that mental retardation was the most common cause of speech delay, accounting for more than 50 percent of cases. In general, the more severe the mental retardation, the slower the acquisition of communicative speech. Speech development is relatively slower in children with mental retardation than in other areas of development.

Research conducted by Khoiriyah, et al. (2016) about children with speech delays found that children who experience delays in speaking are aged 4;0-6;0 years. Children with speech delays tend to be quiet, unable to speak fluently, lack vocabulary mastery, pronunciation of words that are still wrong, expression of sentences that are not clear, slurred, and unable to focus (concentration) at the appointed time.

In this study, directive speech acts were studied. Directive speech acts are speech acts carried out by speakers with the aim of the speech partners performing the actions mentioned in the speech, for example, ordering, pleading, and challenging (Gunarwan, 1994:85-86). In line with this, Yule (1996:93) defines that directive speech acts are speech acts used by speakers to tell others to do something, for example, requests, orders, and giving suggestions. In addition, Ibrahim (1993: 27) states that directive speech acts express the speaker's attitude towards the actions that will be carried out by the speech partner. Ibrahim added six categories of directive speech acts, namely asking, asking, ordering,

forbidding, permitting, suggesting. In line with the opinions of these experts, Rahardi (2005:36) states that directive speech acts are speeches intended by speakers to influence speech partners to take actions, for example ordering, ordering, begging, and advising. According to Clark and Clark (1977:101), directive speech acts are divided into three, namely (a) questions that require answers which, who, why, what, (b) questions with yes/no answers, and (c) orders to do something. something. Based on the three speech acts, those who require the implementation of physical acts are the third.

III. METHOD

This study aims to describe directive speech acts in children with speech delays. This research method is descriptive qualitative. This S (V) is a speech retarded child aged 9;0. However, the language that V understands and produces still suffers from imperfect pronunciation and word deficits. This can be proven by V when he was 9;0 there were still some sound pronunciations that were less than perfect and he pronounced words by omitting some words. The data of this research are utterances in the form of words, phrases, and sentences containing directive speech acts. These utterances were taken when interacting with researchers and the S' family.

In this study, the S is children with speech delays who are classified as having mental retardation. Papalia et al. (2003) said that the developmental speech delay of children aged 2;0 tended to be wrong in pronouncing words, age 3;0 had a poor vocabulary, and age 5;0 had difficulty in naming objects. In analyzing the data, the equivalent method was used. The equivalent method is a method in which the determining tool comes from outside the language in question. To analyze the speech used pragmatic equivalents. Pragmatic equivalents identify linguistic units that arise when the speaker speaks with the speech partner. Reactions that arise when speaking are identified contextually.

The results and research findings obtained from V speech are validated by examining theories and sources. Theoretic triangulation is carried out by researchers by re-understanding the theories that are related to the results and research findings. The results of the examination of the theory were strengthened by researchers by triangulating sources. Triangulation of research sources was carried out on children with speech delays who were the source of triangulation data and other parties who were deemed to be able to understand the results and research findings with critical analysis. After getting the results and findings, the researcher informs this by checking the triangulation data sources.

The results of the examination of the triangulation data sources, therapist teachers, and school teachers, were strengthened by examining the results and findings of related parties who had an understanding of this research. Researchers discussed with fellow researchers about language in children with speech delays. The result of the discussion is that V often shows a word deficit so that the speech conveyed does not show the correct sentence pattern.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In Indonesian, directive speech acts are speech acts that aim to have an impact on the speech partner, such as ordering, demanding, ordering, or giving advice. In this study, directive speech acts were obtained by children with speech delays. The directive speech acts of children with speech delays are explained as follows.

Context		
When P is recording in the bedroom, V approached P to ask for the handphone held by P. Then, P refused V's request.		
Data		Translation
P: (a)	He, jangan diminta!	P: <i>Don't take [my handphone]!</i>
V: (b)	Napa?	V: <i>Why?</i>
P: (c)	Ndak papa.	P: <i>It does not matter.</i>
V: (d)	Ma, minta hp-nya Mama. Ma, liat ini lo, Ma.	V: <i>Lend me your handphone, Mom. I want to take photo.</i>
P: (e)	Lihat apa?	P: <i>What are you looking at?</i>
V: (f)	Ambil hp.	V: <i>Lend me your handphone.</i>
P: (g)	Ndak bisa dipakai Mama.	P: <i>Don't lend me my handphone.</i>

Table 1

The above statement was said by P and V when P was recording with his handphone in the bedroom. When P was recording, V took P's handphone. Then, P said as in (a) forbidding L to take his handphone. V responds to P's command and answers as in speech (b). P's utterance in (c) does not seem to be able to explain the reasons in detail to V. Then, V asks P for something and V wants to show P something like in speech (d). P speaks as in (e) has not been able to accept the meaning of V's speech in (d). P asks V as in speech (e). However, V answered P's question with a question sentence indicated by P as in speech (f). Finally, P gives reason to V as in (g).

Data (1) above contains directive speech acts. The speech act shown by A makes the speech partner do something. The directive speech act is shown by V in (d) in the form of asking. The word *Lend me your handphone* means revealing something in the hope that someone will give something. V in (d) uses the word request marker to show the speech act of asking. In a low tone or a small voice, V asked P to lend him a handphone.

Based on the data above, P begins the speech in (a) namely *Don't take [my handphone]!* V in (b) i.e. *why* did she ask P about the reason why she should not take her handphone. L doesn't like being recorded. Therefore, V felt disturbed. P in (c) is *It does not matter* knew the reason V asked for a handphone so she didn't say the real reason. Because P didn't give a clear reason, V still asked for P's handphone. V wanted a handphone because she didn't want to be recorded. In the speech, V wants P to stop recording and sees V's writing on

(d) namely *Lend me your handphone*. Speech V in (d) contains a directive speech act of asking. This is indicated by the presence of the word *lend* in (d).

P's utterance in (e) is *What are you looking at?* is his disapproval of fulfilling V's request. Therefore, V still wants to take the handphone so that the recording is stopped as in (f) namely *Lend me your handphone*. V's request is still not fulfilled by P in (g) is *Don't lend me my handphone*.

The use of directive speech acts also shows the following data.

Context		
V was silent in the bedroom. Then, V left the room and spoke with P again. However, V looked disappointed that P was still recording V.		
Data		Translation
P: (a)	V main apa sih itu?	P: <i>What are V playing?</i>
V: (b)	Main yo	V: <i>I'm playing.</i>
P: (c)	Mama lho kangen sama kamu. Pingin video kamu?	P: <i>I miss you. I want to make video.</i>
V: (d)	Ma, ma maa, ma maem.	L: <i>Mom, [I want to] eat.</i>
P: (e)	Yo wes maem-maem. Sini!	V: <i>Yes, [I want to take the food].</i>

Table 2

The above story takes place in the bedroom. V is seen entering the bedroom and playing on the bed. Then, P asks V as in speech (a). V did not answer P's question and spoke as in speech (b). P answers the prohibition of V as in speech (c). Suddenly, V spoke to P as in (d) to ask for food. P fulfills V's request as in speech (e). Then, V forbids P as in speech (f) because P seems to be still recording.

Data (2) above shows the directive speech act of asking. The directive speech act asks to show L in (d) namely *Mom, [I want to] eat*. That statement has interpretation, I asked for food and it was said in a low tone to P. V asked P to eat because it was noon. The speech shown by V is a form of action that orders the speech partner to produce a certain effect. Speech V in (d) aims to ask P to get lunch.

P on (a) is *What are you playing?* is a question that contains curiosity about the object being played by V. Then, V in (b) namely *I'm playing* don't want to forbid P to video it. V does not want his playing activities to be disturbed by P. The response shown by P in (c) is *I miss you. I want to make video* gave a reason for wanting to video V. However, V did not respond to P's speech so he in (d) namely *Mom, [I want to] eat* asked P to get food. V in (d) shows the directive speech act of asking even though it is said implicitly.

This was done by V because he had a word deficit in the middle of the sentence. V asked P to get him some food because it was already 11:35 WIB. V's request to P pauses four seconds after P asks him. This is because V walked out of the

room and tried to avoid P. V avoided P because she didn't want to be filmed by her. V at (d) takes four seconds to ask P after P has asked her. The P in (e) is *Yes, [I want to take the food]* fulfill V's request to get a meal together.

The use of directive speech acts also shows the following data.

Context V was seen sitting in front of P. At that time, V was carrying snacks. When V eats, V wants to look at P's handphone to see a message from his teacher.	
Data	Translation
V: (a) Iki lo hp mama.	V: <i>This is mom's handphone.</i>
P: (b) Kenapa hp mama?	P: <i>What's wrong with mom's handphone?</i>
V: (c) Pinjem sek. Lomba jam piro?	V: <i>[Borrow] mom's handphone. What time is the [contest] carnival?</i>
P: (d) Nggak ada.	P: <i>No new chats.</i>

Table 3

The conversation happened when V wanted to see the latest message from his teacher on P's handphone. At that time, V sat in front of P with snacks. P is sitting on the bed with a handphone. When V remembers that there is a competition activity, V speaks to P as in speech (a). P does not seem to understand V's meaning and asks V as in speech (b). V responds to P's question by giving orders and asking P as in speech (c). P understands V's intention that he wants to see the announcement of the competition activities from her teacher. Then, P speaks to V as in speech (d).

The directive speech act of asking is indicated by V in (c) namely *[Borrow] mom's handphone* is a form of requesting speech addressed to P to do an action that V wants. Then, V in (c) wants to borrow the handphone held by P because she wants to see the latest chat from her teacher. L expects P to lend P's handphone. The marker for asking is in the word *borrow*. However, P's response to (d) is nothing informs V that there is no recent chat. Although P in (d) is in the form of refusal, V in (c) shows the directive speech act of asking.

V on (a) is *This is mom's handphone* informed P that she was carrying P's handphone. V on (b) namely *What's wrong with mom's handphone?* has an implicit meaning. P already knew that V didn't just want to show P's handphone, but wanted to convey something. V's limited vocabulary causes him to speak in (c) namely *[Borrow] mom's handphone*. That statement is a form of speech asking P to be willing to lend a handphone. Thus, V in (c) has a requesting speech act. In that speech, V not only wanted to borrow a handphone but also wanted to know the latest information from his class's Whatsapp group. P in (d) is *No new chats* answered the question V after seeing the class Whatsapp group there were no new notifications.

The use of directive speech acts also shows the following data.

Context V was writing in the bedroom, R suddenly went to V. R started to disturb V. However, V forbade R not to disturb while V was writing.	
Data	Translation
V: (a) Oh, sek, Lena, ambilno emmm ambilno ini lo!	V: <i>Wait a minute, Rena, get the ball!</i>
R: (b) Bola.	R: <i>Ball.</i>
V: (c) Ada.	V: <i>There is</i>

Table 4

The conversation between V and R above takes place in the bedroom. Just then, V wrote on the bed. Suddenly, R approached V. Then, R interrupted V while he was writing. Because V was annoyed, she said as in (a) ordered R to fetch something. R responds to V command as in speech (b). V's utterance in (c) responds to R's utterance.

Data (4) above shows that V's speech contains a directive speech act. Directives are used by speakers to order the interlocutor to do something. Commanding speech acts are usually having a high intonation at the beginning and low at the end. The directive speech act shown by V in (a) is in the form of ordering. The V on (a) is *Wait a minute, Rena, get the ball!* aims to command R to take something. V's utterance is also reinforced by a word marker, namely the word *get it* to give orders to R.

V in (a) is *Wait a minute, Rena, get the ball!* indicates a commanding directive speech act. R doesn't respond to V's command because R doesn't understand the command. The V on (a) tell R to pick up the ball. R on (b) namely *The ball* answers V's question. Quickly, V responds to R's answer on (c) is *There is*. The word *there is* spoken by V with the intention that the ball is on the bed.

The use of directive speech acts also shows the following data.

Context V is learning to write in bed, while P is seen looking for crackers. When V finished writing, P offered crackers to V.	
Data	Translation
P: (a) V mau kropok? V mau kropok ndak, V?	P: <i>Do you want crackers or not?</i>
V: (b) Mau.	V: <i>Want to.</i>
P: (c) Mau kropok ini?	P: <i>Do you want these crackers?</i>
V: (d) Mau.	V: <i>Want to.</i>
P: (e) Ini tak kasih.	P: <i>Here I give [one cracker].</i>
V: (f) Makasih, Ma bukakno, Ma!	V: <i>Thank you, Mom, open the cracker wrap crackers, Mom!</i>
P: (g) Hmmm.	P: <i>Hmmm.</i>

Table 5

The conversation happened when V was writing Rena's words on the bed. P is seen dictating V to write Rena's words. When V finished writing Rena's words, P was seen looking for crackers. Then, P offers crackers to V as in speech (c). V answers P's offer as in speech (d). After that, P spoke to V as in (e) gave him a snack. V thanks P as in speech (f). After P gives a packet of crackers, V gives an order to P as in speech (f). The response shown by P was disappointed to V and said as in (g) because P was ordered by V to open the plastic snack. When looking at P's expression, V on (h) picks up the crackers that P has opened.

Data (5) above shows that V's speech contains a commanding directive speech act. The directive speech act of commanding is spoken by V in (f) namely *Open the cracker wrap crackers, Mom!* gave the order to P to open a packet of crackers. V gave the order to P because he found it difficult to open the plastic wrap of the crackers. Therefore, V ordered P to open the plastic. The command indicated by V is marked with an exclamation point (!). In addition, V speaks to P to cause an action to accept or reject. The response shown by P in speech (g) is *Hmmm*, feeling disappointed with her because P was ordered by V again to open the cracker plastic.

Based on the speech above, P in (a) is *Do you want crackers or not?* offered several packets of crackers to V. V in (b) namely *Want to answer P's question.* Next, P in (c) is *Do you want these crackers?* offer other types of crackers. V in (d) namely *Want to emphasize the answer to P's question.* After that, P gives crackers to V so that she says in (e) is *Here I give [one cracker].* V received a packet of crackers from P. However, V could not open the plastic crackers because she was writing. V in (f) namely *Open the cracker wrap crackers, Mom!* ordered P to open the cracker plastic. V in (f) is directive speech act stating command. P in (g) namely *Hmmm* was disappointed because V didn't want to open the cracker plastic. Finally, P opened the cracker plastic and gave it to V.

The use of directive speech acts also shows the following data.

Context	
V is in the classroom, V and A are sitting in chairs, while G is sitting in his chair. A few minutes later, V was disturbed by P who was recording.	
Data	Translation
G: (a) Memunyai apa?	G: <i>[Elephants] have what?</i>
V: (b) Ojok disyuteng!	V: <i>Don't make a video, Mom!</i>

Table 6

The above utterance occurred in the classroom when V returned to the classroom after buying snacks. G sits in her chair opposite V. G gives pictorial questions to V as in speech (a). V spoke as in (b) did not answer G's question. When V spoke as in (b), she seemed to forbid P because he did not want to be recorded.

Data (6) above shows the speech act of the prohibiting directive. The directive speech act of prohibiting is shown by V in (b) namely *Don't make a video, Mom!* The word *don't* say V to influence P. The utterance intends to prohibit P who is behind V from recording. V was disturbed by P when V was receiving lessons from G. The directive speech act that V did in (b) included demanding someone to take action according to the speaker's wishes.

The above statement occurs in the classroom during recess. During recess G in (a) namely *[Elephants]have what?* give questions to V related to the material in the module. When V listened to G give the material, he saw P recording behind him. The V in (b) is *Don't make a video, Mom!* feel disturbed by the activities carried out by P. V in (b) is a speech act prohibiting directive. The speech act of the prohibiting directive is marked with the word *don't*.

The use of directive speech acts also shows the following data.

Context	
V was relaxing on the bed, while R was arranging picture cards. When it was evening, P spoke with R and V.	
Data	Translation
P: (a) Ayo, R mandi dulu!	P: <i>Come on, R take a shower now!</i>
R: (b) Pake ini.	R: <i>Brought this [picture card with me]</i>
P: (c) Masukkan ini!	P: <i>Insert [picture card] here.</i>
V: (d) Ndak bole basah.	V: <i>Don't take the card to to the bathroom.</i>

Table 7

The utterances between P, R, and V above occur in the bedroom. At that time, V was relaxing on the bed, while R was arranging picture cards. When it was evening, P ordered R to take a bath as in (a). R's utterance in (b) responds to P's command with the condition that R brings a picture card while bathing. P tells R to put it in the cardholder as in speech (c). V's statement in (d) forbids R to bring a picture card while bathing. Then, P explained to R the reason why he couldn't bring a picture card when taking a shower.

Data (7) above shows that V's utterance contains a prohibiting directive speech act. The directive speech act forbids showing V's speech in (d) namely *Don't take the card to to the bathroom.* The utterance prohibits R from using performative declarative sentences. Performative declarative sentences are sentences that have the effect of an action on what the speaker says. V informs R that the picture card should not be taken in the shower because the card will get wet. In this utterance, V forbids R with the word *ndak bole* to indicate the prohibiting directive speech act. The utterance shown by V affects R to act. The response shown by R is the act of putting a picture card on the bed.

Based on the data above, P in (a) is *Come on, R take a shower now!* started the speech by ordering R to be ready to take a shower because it was late. R is willing to take a shower, but with the condition that the card she is holding is also taken to the bathroom as in (b) namely *Brought this [picture card with me]*. P on (c) is *Insert [picture card] here* does not agree if R takes a bath with a picture card. Therefore, P tells R to put a picture card into the cardholder. V in (d) is *Don't take the card to to the bathroom* agrees to P's command on R. V's utterance contains a prohibiting directive speech act.

The use of directive speech acts can also be seen in the following data.

Context	
P and V's conversation took place in the corridor in front of the bedroom. At that time, V and P were preparing to go to therapy. When V wants to leave, V orders P to immediately go to therapy.	
Data	Translation
V: (a) Ayo, Ma!	V: <i>Let's go to [hospital], Mom.</i>
P: (b) Moh, nggak mau jawab di mana terapinya?	P: <i>I don't want [to accompany] because I haven't answered where the therapy is.</i>
V: (c) He, he, ayo Ma!	V: <i>Let's go to [hospital], Mom!</i>
P: (d) Jawab dulu terapinya di mana?	P: <i>Where is the therapy?</i>
V: (d) Ayo, Ma! (berjalan menuju ruang tamu)	V: <i>Let's go to [hospital], Mom!</i>

Table 8

The conversation between P and V above takes place in the corridor in front of the family room. P and V are preparing because they want to go to therapy. When V is finished, P records V so that V's speech in (a) orders P to leave immediately. P's utterance in (b) refuses V's command because V's previous question still hasn't answered. Then, V emphasizes his command to P as in speech (c).

Data (8) above shows that V's speech contains a directive speech act of inviting. The speech act of inviting is shown by V in (a) and (c). V's statement in (a) is *Let's go to [hospital], Mom* invites P to immediately be sent to therapy. The invitation marker used is *come on*. The word *let* is a word marker used in the invitation sentence. The invitation spoken by V contains action. However, the response shown by P in (b) is *I don't want [to accompany] because I haven't answered where the therapy is?* refused V's invitation to immediately go to therapy. Because it gets a rejection from P, V in (c) namely *Let's go to [hospital], Mom!* also shows the act of inviting. The speech reaffirmed that P complied with her wish to immediately go to the therapy center.

Based on data (8) above, V in (a) started her speech by inviting P. However, P in (b) did not fulfill V's command. A few moments later, V in (c) was *He, he, come on, Ma!* reaffirmed his invitation to P.

The speech in data (8) occurs when V wants to go to therapy. Because the time was already 1:39 pm, V walked into the living room so he said to (a) namely *Let's go to [hospital], Mom* However, the response shown by P in (b) is *I don't want [to accompany] because I haven't answered where the therapy is?* is a form of rejection of P because V did not answer the question he asked. Because it gets a rejection from P, V in (c) namely *Let's go to [hospital], Mom!* shows the speech act of inviting P. The speech reaffirmed that P complied with his wish to immediately go to the therapy center. P in (d) is *Where is the therapy?* ask V again and walking towards the living room while recording, following V from behind while recording. V saw that P was still recording so he said to (d) that is *Let's go to [hospital], Mom!* invites P to immediately go to therapy.

The use of directive speech acts also shows the following data.

Context	
After V played with R in the bedroom, V was seen walking towards the corridor. At that time, V felt hungry. Then, P followed V and had a conversation with him.	
Data	Translation
P: (a) Ayo, katanya maem!	P: <i>Come on, you said eat!</i>
V: (b) Iyo, iyo.	V: <i>Ok, Moms.</i>
P: (c) Maem apa?	P: <i>What do you want eat?</i>
V: (d) Soto.	V: <i>Soto.</i>
P: (e) Soto, kamu suka soto ta?	P: <i>Soto, do you like soto?</i>
V: (f) Ayo, maem!	V: <i>Let's eat!</i>

Table 9

The conversation took place in the corridor after V and R played in the room. After they played, P walked into the corridor and spoke as in (a). V answers P's command as in speech (c). Since V's response is slow, P asks V as in (d). Firmly, V answers question P as in (e). P reaffirmed V's answer and then asked why V liked Soto. However, V did not answer P's question because he wanted to eat immediately so he invited P as in speech (f).

Data (9) above shows that utterance V contains a directive speech act of inviting. The directive speech act invites V to speak in (f) namely *Come on, maem!* The word *let's* be used by V as a sign of an invitation to P. V invites P to immediately get the Soto food in the kitchen.

Based on the data above, the speech occurred when V and R finished playing in the bedroom. After playing, P on (a) is *Come on, he says maem! Mam what?* invites V to eat. Forcedly, V accepts V's invitation so he speaks to (b) namely *Yes, yes.* After V answered P's invitation about dinner, P in (c) i.e. *Maem what?* offered a menu to V. Then, V in (d) *soto* answered P's question. V said *soto* because he knew that N cooked *soto*. The P on (e) is *Soto, do you like soto?* Asked again what menu V wanted and asked why he liked *soto*. Because V was hungry, V did not respond to P. V's question

on (f) namely *Come on, maem!* is V's invitation to P to eat immediately. V invites P intending to immediately get soup because he is hungry. The word let spoken by V is a directive speech act of inviting.

The use of directive speech acts also shows the following data.

Context	
When P was recording in the bedroom, V approached P to ask for the handphone that P was holding. Then, P refused V's request.	
Data	Translation
P: (a) He, jangan diminta!	P: <i>Don't take mom's handphone!</i>
V: (b) Kenapa?	V: <i>Why can't you take your handphone?</i>
P: (c) Ndak papa.	P: <i>I want to use [handphone]</i>
V: (d) Ma, minta penya Mama. Ma, liat ini lo, Ma.	V: <i>I want to borrow mom's handphone. Mom, I want take photo of my writing.</i>
P: (e) Lihat apa?	P: <i>Do you want a photo of your writing??</i>
V: (f) Ambil hp?	V: <i>Borrow mom's handphone</i>
P: (g) Ndak bisa dipakai mama.	P: <i>I want to use my handphone</i>

Table 10

The above story takes place in the bedroom. At that time, P was recording with his handphone in the bedroom. When P was recording, V took P's handphone. Then, P said as in (a) forbidding V to take her handphone. V responds to P's command and answers as in speech (b). P's utterance in (c) does not seem to be able to explain the reasons in detail to V. Then, V asks P for something and V wants to show P something like in speech (d). P speaks as in (e) has not been able to accept the meaning of V's speech in (d). P asks V as in speech (e). However, V answered P's question with a question sentence indicated by P as in speech (f). Finally, P gives reason to V as in (g).

Data (10) above contains a directive speech act indicated by V in (b) in the form of asking. V in (b) is *Why can't you take your handphone?* The word marker *why* to show the speech act of asking the reason not to borrow a handphone. V hopes that P will give reasons for not lending her handphone.

Based on the data above, P begins the speech in (a) namely *Don't take mom's handphone!* ordered V not to take P's handphone which was used for recording. V in (b) is *Why can't you take your handphone?* V doesn't like being recorded. Therefore, V felt disturbed. Speech V in (b) is a directive speech act asking. The marker shown by V in the speech is *why*. The word *why* is used to ask the cause or reason for an event to occur. P in (c) namely *I want to use [handphone]* knew the reason V asked for a handphone so he didn't say the real reason. Because P didn't give a clear reason, V still asked

for P's handphone. V wanted a handphone because he didn't want to be recorded. In this speech, V wants P to stop recording and sees V's writing on (d) which is *I want to borrow mom's handphone. Mom, I want take photo of my writing.*

The use of directive speech acts also shows the following data.

Context	
In the room, V is learning to read a theme book. Then, V flipped through the pages of the theme book to find something to read. Feeling difficult, V asked P for help.	
Data	Translation
P: (a) V, ada PR bahasa Jawa ndak?	P: <i>V, Is there a Java homework?</i>
V: (b) Ini diapain? (membalik halaman buku tematik)	V: <i>How to do that [homework]?</i>
P: (c) Hem...	P: <i>Hem...</i>
V: (d) Ini diapain?	V: <i>How to do that [homework]?</i>
P: (e) Baca perintahnya	P: <i>Read the command that [homework]</i>

Table 11

The speech above begins when P asks V as in speech (a). P asked V because he was still studying together with P in the bedroom. V does not answer P's question and asks her as in speech (b). P speaks as in (c) to V because V does not answer the question. Since question V is not answered by P, V asks P again as in (d). P does not respond to V's question and asks her as in speech (e). Finally, V answers the question P as in speech (f).

Data (11) above shows that V's speech shows the directive speech act of asking. The directive speech act of asking is shown by V's speech in (b) namely *How to do that [homework]?* The speech act is shown in the word *how*.

The speech above begins with the question P to V. P in (a) is *V, is there a Java homework?* asked V because seeing the situation it was night and V was still studying. V in (b) namely *How to do that [homework]?* did not answer the question P. V asked P because he found it difficult to do schoolwork. The utterance is included in the directive speech act of asking. V uses what marker to show the directive speech act of asking.

P in (c) is *Hem...* clears his throat because V hasn't answered his question. Strictly speaking, V in (d) namely *How to do that [homework]?* still seems to ask P because P has not answered the question. P in (e) is *Read the command that [homework]* tells V to reread the command on the PR.

In this study, S has been able to use the directive speech acts of asking, ordering, and prohibiting. The similarity of this research with the research of Yusri, et al. (2019) with S children with autism are S can use the three directive speech acts, while the difference is that S in this study has not been able to use advice speech acts and recommendation speech

acts. S in this study has not been able to use directive speech acts of advice and recommendations because of limited vocabulary and poor intellectual abilities.

The findings of this study are the same as Yani's (2017) research, namely S has been able to use directive speech acts to command, invite, and ask. Yani studied autistic children in the categories of mild, moderate, and severe. The findings show that children with autism dominate the use of nonverbal language in responding to directive speech. Meanwhile, mild autistic children can use verbal language to respond to directive speech acts. Mild autistic children had a better response than moderate and severely autistic children. However, moderate and severely autistic children were also able to respond well to directive speech. The speech act responses are shown by S when responding such as commanding, pleading, ordering, urging, inviting, obeying, and asking. This study has similarities with the research conducted by Wardiani and Hazmi (2018), namely, S can use directive speech acts asking, asking, ordering, and prohibiting.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of data analysis, it can be concluded as follows. V can use directive speech acts. The directive speech acts used by V ordering, forbidding, inviting, and asking. The number of utterances shown by V in speech acts, namely the speech act of asking for 3 utterances, the speech act of commanding as many as 3 utterances, the speech act of prohibiting as many as 9 utterances, the speech act of inviting as many as 7 utterances, and the speech act of asking as many as 7 utterances. Thus, the most dominant directive speech act is a prohibiting speech act.

Based on the three research findings above, it can be concluded that the majority of children with speech delays and autism are able to use the speech act of asking and ordering. This is because S has a limited vocabulary so that the speech acts that are often used are asking and ordering.

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